

QUALITY ASSESSMENT OF 2% LIDOCAINE INJECTABLE SOLUTIONS USED IN DENTAL CLINICS IN YAOUNDE, CAMEROON

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ABSTRACT

Background: Local anesthetics, particularly 2% lidocaine, are essential in dental practice. The quality of injectable formulations directly affects patient safety and therapeutic effectiveness. Substandard medicines remain a concern in low- and middle-income countries. **Objective:** To evaluate the physicochemical, microbiological, and labeling quality of 2% lidocaine injectable solutions used in dental clinics in Yaoundé, Cameroon. **Methods:** A descriptive and analytical study was conducted between November 2018 and July 2019. Fifteen batches of 2% lidocaine were collected from 11 dental clinics using consecutive sampling. Each batch underwent labeling inspection, visual examination, microbiological testing, pH measurement, and active ingredient assay using UV-visible spectrophotometry. Results were expressed as means ± standard deviation, proportions, and 95% confidence intervals (95% CI). **Results:** Among the 15 batches analyzed, 80% originated from India, 13% from France, and 7% from Spain.

Two batches (13.3%; 95% CI: 1.7–40.5%) showed labeling

non-conformities. All samples were clear and sterile. Four batches (26.7%; 95% CI: 7.8–55.1%) had pH values below pharmacopoeial standards. The lidocaine concentration was compliant in all samples (mean: 2.01% \pm 0.04%; 95% CI: 1.97–2.05%). **Conclusion:** Most analyzed batches complied with quality standards; however, labeling deficiencies and pH deviations were observed. Regular quality control and strengthened pharmaceutical surveillance are recommended.

KEYWORDS: Quality control; Lidocaine 2%; Injectable drugs; Dental anesthesia; Cameroon.

INTRODUCTION

Local anesthetics are widely used in dentistry to provide pain-free surgical and restorative procedures.^[1] Lidocaine, an amide-type local anesthetic, is commonly administered at a 2% concentration and may be combined with epinephrine to prolong anesthetic action and reduce bleeding.^[2,3]

Although considered safe and effective, injectable anesthetics require strict quality standards to prevent adverse reactions, including local anesthetic systemic toxicity (LAST).^[4] Substandard and falsified medicines remain a significant public health challenge worldwide, particularly in low- and middle-income countries.^[5] In Cameroon, previous studies have documented quality deficiencies in essential medicines circulating within the pharmaceutical supply chain.^[6]

Physicochemical parameters such as pH and active ingredient concentration are critical determinants of stability, sterility, and therapeutic effectiveness of injectable drugs.^[7,8] Therefore, continuous post-marketing quality surveillance is essential to ensure patient safety. Recent international reviews highlight ongoing research into lidocaine's clinical use and formulation stability, emphasizing the need to consider physicochemical factors such as pH in injectable solutions.^[9,10] Furthermore, advances in pharmaceutical quality control methodologies underline the importance of rigorous quality assurance practices across drug products.^[11]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design

A descriptive and analytical study was conducted from November 25, 2018, to July 11, 2019.

Sampling

Fifteen batches of 2% lidocaine injectable solutions were collected consecutively from 11 dental clinics in Yaoundé. Products were transported under appropriate storage conditions to the Multidisciplinary Laboratory of the Department of Pharmaceutics, University of Yaounde I.

Quality Control Tests

- 1. Labeling inspection:** Compliance with Good Manufacturing Practices and regulatory labeling requirements.
- 2. Visual examination:** Clarity and absence of visible particles.
- 3. Microbiological testing:** Detection of bacteria, yeasts, and molds using Thioglycollate and Mueller-Hinton media.
- 4. Physicochemical analysis:**
 - pH measured using a calibrated BENCHTOP 210 pH meter.
 - Lidocaine assay performed by UV-Visible spectrophotometry according to Beer-Lambert law.

Statistical Analysis

Given the small sample size and non-probabilistic sampling, analysis was strictly descriptive. Quantitative variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation and 95% CI. Qualitative variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages. Analyses were performed using Microsoft Excel 2013.

RESULTS

Origin of Batches

Twelve batches (80%) were manufactured in India, two (13%) in France, and one (7%) in Spain (figure 1).

Figure 1. Origin batches.

Labeling Compliance

Two batches (13.3%; 95% CI: 1.7–40.5%) showed labeling deficiencies.

Visual and Microbiological Assessment

All samples were clear and free of visible particles. No microbial growth was detected after 14 days of incubation.

Physicochemical Results

The proportion of non-compliant samples was 26.7% (4/15 batches) for pH and 0% for lidocaine concentration. Figure 2 shows the mean pH and lidocaine concentration (%) of analyzed batches.

Figure 2. Mean pH and lidocaine concentration (%) of analyzed batches with 95% confidence intervals.

DISCUSSION

The majority of analyzed batches complied with sterility and active ingredient requirements. However, labeling deficiencies were identified. Inadequate labeling may compromise traceability and safe administration, particularly for injectable medicines.^[12]

Pharmacopoeial standards emphasize the importance of maintaining appropriate pH ranges for injectable lidocaine to ensure stability and reduce pain upon injection.^[13] Deviations may result from improper storage conditions or manufacturing variability.^[14] The observed deviations in pH align with findings from studies examining lidocaine stability under different preparatory conditions, reinforcing that pH can significantly affect formulation stability and performance.^[10]

Similar studies conducted in sub-Saharan Africa have reported irregularities in the quality of essential injectable medicines, highlighting persistent regulatory challenges in pharmaceutical markets.^[6,13,14]

CONCLUSION

2% lidocaine injectable solutions used in dental clinics in Yaoundé are generally compliant with quality standards. Nonetheless, detected irregularities emphasize the need for strengthened regulatory oversight and improved storage monitoring.

DECLARATIONS

Ethical Approval: This study did not involve human or animal subjects. It evaluated commercially available pharmaceutical products.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Authors' Contributions: All authors contributed to study conception, laboratory analysis, manuscript drafting, and approved the final version.

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